

STUDIES ON VITAMIN-A IN SOLUTION. PART III. INITIAL LOSS OF POTENCY AND FUNCTION OF HYDROGEN DONATING SUBSTANCE

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The loss of vitamin-A in solution may be better controlled if the substrate be previously adjuvated with suitable antioxidant. In such a function a hydrogen donating substance plays no special part when the substrate is a natural or synthetic, saturated or unsaturated glyceride or ester. The above hydrogen donating substance has no appreciable antioxygenic function.

In part II of this series (Basu and Bhattacharya, this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 459) mention has been made of the observation that vitamin-A alcohol when dissolved in glycerides or esters, whether natural or synthetic, saturated or unsaturated, loses a portion of its potency which has been termed as "initial loss". But this initial loss was not experienced when either vitamin-A alcohol was dissolved in liquid paraffin or when vitamin-A acetate was diluted with esters, saturated or unsaturated. Attempts were made to vary the conditions of experiment so as to find out the methods by which this initial loss of potency in vitamin-A alcohol might be prevented. In course of experiments carried out for finding the mode of action of the antioxidant, it was noticed (Basu and Bhattacharya, *loc. cit.*) that oleic acid exerted a synergistic action on the antioxidant in case where the substrate was liquid paraffin. But it has now been found that oleic acid itself has practically no antioxygenic function, neither it has been found to potentiate the antioxygenic function of propyl gallate to any appreciable degree when the substrate is arachis oil, ethyl oleate or ethyl stearate. The results of all these experiments have been embodied in the present paper. The paper is based on a pending patent application.

EXPERIMENTAL

Studies on the Initial Loss of Potency in Vitamin-A Alcohol.—Vitamin-A concentrate used had 1×10^4 I.U. per g. of vitamin-A potency; *n*-propyl gallate of m.p. 146-48°; oleic acid of B.P. specification; arachis oil, ethyl oleate and ethyl stearate had the characteristics described in part I of this series (Basu and Bhattacharya, *ibid.*, 1949, 26, 419). Vitamin-A acetate was of U.S.P. reference standard quality and liquid paraffin of B.P. specification had been used in this investigation. Oleic acid and propyl gallate used were 0.21% and 0.05% respectively in all cases. Variations in the method of preparation were made and the details will be found in column (a) of Table I. Accurately weighed amounts of the above vitamin-A concentrate, which had been previously assayed for its vitamin-A potency, was dissolved in 25 c.c. of arachis oil or liquid paraffin but in the case of vitamin-A acetate, two gelatine capsules, each containing 2500 I.U. of vitamin-A per capsule, were taken into 10 g. of the substrate, ethyl oleate or ethyl stearate, and the tips of the capsules were cut off with a fine scissors. The theoretical potency of each of the preparations was calculated which will be found in column (c) in Table I. Representative sample from each of the preparations was weighed and assayed for its vitamin-A content by the method described in part I of this series (Basu and Bhattacharya, *loc. cit.*). The results of these analyses are recorded in column (b) of Table I.

Oleic Acid as an Antioxidant.—To ascertain any antioxygenic function of oleic

acid, vitamin-A concentrate was diluted with liquid paraffin in such a way that each gramme of the preparation contained 1100 I.U. of vitamin-A. This preparation was adjvated with 0.21% oleic acid and was taken in an amber-coloured resistant bottle fitted with perforated cork to allow introduction of glass tubings for aeration. Pure and dry air at the rate of 4 c.c. per second was passed through the system and samples withdrawn at intervals were assayed for their vitamin-A content in the usual way. The results are recorded in the first two columns of Table II. The loss of potency of vitaminised liquid paraffin (i) without antioxidant, (ii) with antioxidant and (iii) with antioxidant and oleic acid are also shown in Table II for comparison.

Synergistic Action of a Hydrogen donating Substance

Oleic Acid in Glyceride or Ester System.—Oleic acid, when present with an antioxidant in vitaminised liquid paraffin system, acts as a regenerator of the bound antioxidant and as a result vitamin-A potency is better protected. This observation suggests for study the action of a hydrogen donating substance on an antioxidant when the substance is externally added to a vitaminised ester or glyceride system. Accordingly vitamin-A concentrate was dissolved in arachis oil, ethyl oleate and ethyl stearate separately. A portion (25 c.c.) of each of the preparations was fortified with 0.05% propyl gallate and another 25 c.c. portion of each was adjvated with 0.21% oleic acid in addition to 0.05% propyl gallate. The preparations were taken in amber-coloured resistant bottles for aeration. Vitamin-A content of each was determined initially and at intervals during aeration. The results of these experiments will be found in Tables III, IV and V.

TABLE I

*Initial loss of potency in vitamin-A alcohol **

Expt. No.	Details of preparation. (a)	Vitamin-A potency		Recovery.
		Found (I.U./g.) (b)	Calculated (I.U./g.) (c)	
1.	Oleic acid was mixed up with vitamin-A at first and then diluted with arachis oil.	1184	1478	80.1%
2.	Propyl gallate was mixed up with vitamin-A at first and then diluted with arachis oil.	920	1043	88.2
3.	Propyl gallate was mixed up with oleic acid, vitamin-A was added to this mixture and the mixture was finally diluted with arachis oil.	1109	1243	89.2
4.	Arachis oil was adjvated with oleic acid and to this oil was added vitamin-A.	832	1156	71.9
5.	Arachis oil was adjvated with propyl gallate and to this oil was added vitamin-A.	1275	1273	100.4
6.	Propyl gallate was mixed up with oleic acid, to this mixture was added arachis oil and then vitamin-A was added to this mixture.	1168	1170	99.8
7.	Vitamin-A was dissolved in liquid paraffin.	1160	1155	100.4
8.	Vitamin-A acetate was dissolved in ethyl oleate.	496	500	99.2
9.	Vitamin-A acetate was dissolved in ethyl stearate.	503	500	100.6

* Oleic acid in the system is 0.21% and propyl gallate, 0.05% in all cases, where they are present.

TABLE II

Oleic acid as an antioxidant.

Substrate—Liquid paraffin.

Aerated for	With 0.21% oleic acid.		Without antioxidant.		With antioxidant.		With antioxidant and oleic acid.	
	Vitamin-A (I.U./g.)	% Loss of vitamin-A.	Vitamin-A (I.U./g.)	% Loss of vitamin-A.	Vitamin-A (I.U./g.)	% Loss of vitamin-A.	Vitamin-A (I.U./g.)	% Loss of vitamin-A.
0	1100	0	1100	0	1100	0	1100	0
87 hrs.	495	55.0	512	53.5	658	40.2	773	29.7
142	275	75.0	305	72.3	620	43.7	755	31.4
190	200	81.8	224	79.8	610	44.6	750	31.8

TABLE III *

Synergistic action of oleic acid.

Substrate—Arachis oil.

Aerated for	With antioxidant		With antioxidant and oleic acid	
	Vitamin-A (I.U./g.)	% Loss of vitamin-A.	Vitamin-A (I.U./g.)	% Loss of vitamin-A.
0	1280	0	1280	0
40 hrs.	997	22.1	—	—
54	—	—	1024	20.0
75	—	—	983	23.2
80	939	26.6	—	—
150	—	—	925	27.7
165	851	33.5	—	—

* Oleic acid in the systems is 0.21% and antioxidant, 0.05% in all cases, where they are present.

TABLE IV *

Synergistic action of oleic acid.

Substrate—Ethyl oleate.

Aerated for	With antioxidant		With antioxidant and oleic acid	
	Vitamin-A (I.U./g.)	% Loss of vitamin-A.	Vitamin-A (I.U./g.)	% Loss of vitamin-A.
0.	1194	0	1194	0
58 hrs.	1053	11.8	992	16.9
135	...	...	885	25.9
142	855	28.4	...	...
188	...	...	777	34.9
190	714	40.2	...	...

* Oleic acid in the systems is 0.21% and antioxidant, 0.05% in all cases, where they are present.

TABLE V *

Synergistic action of oleic acid.

Substrate—Ethyl stearate.

Aerated for	With antioxidant		With antioxidant and oleic acid	
	Vitamin A (I.U./g.)	% Loss of vitamin-A ^a	Vitamin-A (I.U./g.)	% Loss of vitamin-A.
0	1229	0	1229	0
47 hrs.	1113	9.4	...	...
54	...	..	1060	13.7
96	1022	16.8	...	...
128	...	...	972	20.9
158	864	29.7	...	...
180	...	...	803	34.0

* Oleic acid in the systems is 0.21% and antioxidant, 0.05% in all cases, where they are present.

DISCUSSION

From the results of the experiment Nos. 1 to 3 of Table I it will be found that when oleic acid or propyl gallate, either individually or both combined at a time, is admixed with vitamin-A alcohol initially and then diluted with arachis oil, the vitamin-A alcohol loses from 10.8 to 19.9% of its potency. The system of arachis oil, when initially adjuvated with oleic acid and then with vitamin-A, loses 28.1% of the calculated vitamin-A potency (cf. Expt. No. 4, Table I). But when the archis oil is mixed up with antioxidant initially and then vitamin-A alcohol is added, the preparation retains all its vitamin-A activity (cf. Expt. No. 5, Table I). Addition of oleic acid and antioxidant to the oil and then vitamin-A also keeps the vitamin-A potency to the same degree. In expt. Nos. 7 to 9 vitamin-A alcohol, when dissolved in liquid paraffin or vitamin-A acetate when incorporated in esters, saturated or unsaturated, does not lose any vitamin-A activity.

From these results it appears that the peroxide-like compounds of the substrate are responsible for the initial loss of potency of vitamin-A alcohol. The incorporation of an antioxidant in the oil, prior to the addition of vitamin-A, may form a complex with the peroxide-like body of the oil to remove it from the phase of reaction and thereby prevent the destruction of vitamin-A molecule. But if the antioxidant is adjuvated after the vitamin-A has been added to oil, the peroxide of the oil, already present, may cause deterioration of the vitamin-A molecule. Then the antioxidant would only function to prevent any further formation of peroxide (cf. Basu and Bhattacharya, *loc. cit.*).

C O N C L U S I O N

The initial loss of potency of vitamin-A, when dissolved in esters or glycerides, may be prevented by the incorporation of an antioxidant to the substrates in the first instance and then adding the vitamin-A concentrate. The antioxidant combines with the peroxide-like compounds of the substrates to remove them from the phase of reaction and thus prevents those peroxides to act on vitamin-A molecule.

A hydrogen donating substance, e.g., oleic acid itself does not play the part of an antioxidant but acts as a synergistic agent on the antioxidant.

Such hydrogen donating substance, when present in an ester or glyceride system in addition to antioxidant, does not show any special effect. The incipient formation of a free acid in these systems is sufficient to act as a synergistic agent.

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